

doi:10.5281/zenodo.4966552

TEACHING PRESCHOOL STUDENTS THE SKILL OF SHARING VIA PHILOSOPHICAL APPROACH: A PROGRAM EXAMPLE

S.Sunay Yildirim Doğru*

Süleyman Doğru**

H.Bilge Doğru***

Prof.Dr. - Asistan Prof.

Dokuz Eylül University, Turkey

sunay.dogru@deu.edu.tr*

[https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0573-0128*](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0573-0128)

Abstract. *Philosophy education with children aims to support children in building their reasoning structures, to teach them to justify their views by enabling them to think critically and creatively, to express their thoughts through discussion and to understand others, and to develop an inquisitive way of thinking as a democratic and effective citizen. This education covers a wide spectrum from preschool educators to higher education educators in terms of demonstrating that children of all ages can do philosophy. Although children do not have the practice of doing philosophy, they all have the capacity to do so. All children can think about epistemological and metaphysical ideas, and they can generate creative and new ideas. The important thing is to present this learning opportunity to children with the right program. The aim of this study is to design an example of a program with a philosophical approach in teaching sharing skills to preschool students. In the program prepared, a story book was analyzed by using the SAPERE P4C Approach. The story book was transformed into a philosophical discussion program.*

Key words: *sharing skills, Philosophical education, preschool student.*

Вступ

Introduction

Philosophy for children is a critical thinking education program put forward by the American philosopher Matthew Lipman (1922-2010) in the 1970s. In this approach, it is aimed to develop the thinking skills of children with philosophical dialogue. When we look at the history of philosophy, the essence of philosophy is the feeling of curiosity and the desire to understand the world in which people live. Human asks various questions while trying to understand anything they are curious about and in fact, they try to answer anything they worry about with questions. When looking at the practice of philosophy education for children in Turkey, in Direk's (2016) book, *Thinking About The Little Prince*, it is stated that the philosophical thinking that is desired to be taught to children through philosophy education should be gained at an early age. According to him, philosophy education is based on questioning. Thus, it is necessary to start this education at a young age. In addition, children's large imagination is a factor that will increase the need for them to meet philosophy at an early age (Direk, 2016; Ögüt, 2019). According to Direk (2016), philosophy education for children should enable children to express the concepts through dialogue and discussion by using text, story, newspaper article or daily life experiences. It also contributes to the children to make evaluations based on both their readings and their experiences (AkkocaoğluÇayır, 2015). Thus, children will learn and develop philosophical thinking by getting acquainted with philosophy.

Science limited to books taught in schools consists of classical approaches. Therefore, It is important to gain skills in children and young people such as realizing the existing situation at the social level, evaluation, expressing current and future problems and solutions within the framework of mental norms, understanding the importance of questioning and deeply knowing the human-world-knowledge framework, being able to look at problems, facts and events from multiple angles and critical thinking. Although children do not have the practice of doing philosophy, all children have the capacity to do so. "Philosophy for Children" is a teaching method. Teaching philosophy is not teaching the history or content of philosophy. This method can be used in all fields except philosophy. Therefore, one side of this educational approach is based on philosophy and the other side on educational sciences. In academic philosophy, in a philosophy course, some basic concepts, philosophers, or the course of basic philosophical debates are conveyed. "Philosophy for Children" teaches children to apply thinking skills in their daily life rather than make them memorize information. The most important feature of this approach is that it is not a lecture, but a method, a community work.

Методи та методики дослідження ***Methods and Techniques of the Research***

Nelson's Socratic Method: According to Nelson, the Socratic Method is not the art of teaching philosophical knowledge, but the art of teaching philosophical thinking skills. In other words, It is the art of making students philosophers, not of giving information about philosophers. For Nelson, everyday real experiences should be an object of philosophizing like looking at someone's coat because, philosophy is in our understanding of these experiences in which philosophical truth takes place (McCall, 2013; Demirtaş, Karadağ ve Gülenç, 2018).

McCall's FST Method: The "I agree / disagree because..." pattern used in the FST reasoning structure is designed for children to place their arguments in a logical relationship with the arguments of other children. The aim is to listen to the opinions and arguments of others, to clarify the relationships between the arguments or perspectives presented, to test the arguments with counter-arguments, to provide justifications, and to evaluate the reasons which put forward (McCall, 2013).

Lipman's P4C Program: P4C programs are based on John Dewey's pragmatic philosophy. Dewey suggested that when humans interact with the environment, they transform the environment and therefore, he expressed that there is not a fixed knowledge, but a process that is constantly transforming. Thus, Lipman emphasized the democratic practice of children being co-creators of meaning. In Lipman's P4C application, structuring the meaning is a priority (Lipman, 2003).

SAPERE P4C Approach: SAPERE's approach focuses directly on establishing philosophical dialogues about certain episodes from stories, poems or films that can start a debate on philosophical issues. The aim is to help children to reason, form and ask questions, participate in constructive discussions, and develop arguments. P4C Education aims to provide skills through Philosophy for Children education to children such as recognizing the existing situation at the social level, evaluation, expressing current and future problems and solution productions within the framework of mental norms, understanding the importance of questioning and deeply knowing the human-world-knowledge framework, being able to look at problems, facts and events from multiple angles, critical thinking. P4C is a holistic school approach. It can be used in all subjects,

individuals of all ages and abilities (including individuals with special needs) throughout the curriculum. The P4C Instructor's job is to be a facilitator (McCall, 2013; Boyacı, Karadağ ve Gülenç, 2018).

Philosophizing is not the same as learning the history of philosophy. It is possible to learn how to philosophize without learning the history of philosophy, but practice is absolutely necessary to achieve it. All children can think about epistemological and metaphysical ideas, have discussions, and come up with new ideas. The important thing is to offer children this opportunity to learn. The aim of this study is to design a program example with a philosophical approach in teaching sharing skills to preschool students. In the program prepared, a storybook was analyzed using the SAPERE P4C Approach. The storybook was transformed into a philosophical discussion program.

In this study, a program analysis sample has been prepared in accordance with the SAPERE P4C philosophical approach.

SAPERE P4C Approach: SAPERE's approach focuses directly on establishing philosophical dialogues about certain episodes from stories, poems or films that can start a debate on philosophical issues. The aim is to help children to reason, form and ask questions, participate in constructive discussions, and develop arguments. In this approach, students learn;

- Philosophical Concept and Knowledge,
- Reasoning and Inquiry (Argumentation),
- Analytical Thinking Skills,
- Critical Thinking Skills,
- Expression and Writing Skills,
- Being Philosophical Literate,
- Generating Original Ideas,
- Ability to Philosophize with Other Children,
- Listening and respecting each other,
- Being open in their thoughts, making responsible and deliberate judgments,
- To be more considerate by basing their decisions and actions on reasons. In addition,

P4C encourages openness to other people's opinions and perspectives.

Planning process; In this study, philosophical analysis of the storybook named "Should I Share My Ice Cream?" by Mo Willems is made. The order for this process is as follows;

- Summary
- Guidelines for Philosophical Discussion
- Questions for Philosophical Discussion
 1. What is sharing?
 2. Who is Best Friend?
 3. Feeling Disappointment
 4. Concept of Right and Wrong
 5. The Nature of Hesitation

Subtitles were created for the questions in this section and the questions were detailed. In this process, it is aimed to develop critical thinking skills of questioning and curious children with philosophical thinking because, after childhood, people stop asking and questioning and lose their curiosity. Children are expected to grow up as thinking and productive individuals with philosophy education for children. Socrates mentioned the importance of thinking years ago by saying "*Speak your own thoughts, not what you have read and heard, but what is happening within you. Grow the saplings of your own garden*

by getting rid of the habit of eating fruit from other people's trees. Then you will enjoy the pleasure of eating fruit.” to his students (Özkan, 2020).

During the implementation process; Before starting to read, examples of questions for pre-conversation are included (Asking children if they like ice cream, which flavor do they like most?). During the reading process, regarding the application: it has been tried make children to think about the story and to get involved in the process with asking questions like “who are the main characters” etc. At the end of the reading; "Begin by filling out Story Matrix" was created. The story matrix is as follows;

Story Matrix:

should he does? Is it what best friends do?

•Elephant thinks to share his ice cream with his best friend.	Yes	Yes
•Elephant thinks his best friend does not like the flavor of ice cream so he shouldn't share it.	Yes (he may ask Piggy if he likes the flavor)	No

Discussion questions were created to make discussions on the subject after the reading.

Questions for Discussion: (Select questions from your book module)

1. Should Elephant share his ice cream with Piggy? If the answer is yes then why?
2. Is sharing a right thing?
3.

As we mentioned before, P4C is a holistic school approach. It can be used for all subjects throughout the curriculum, students with all ages and abilities. For this reason, it is thought that the analysis of the program will be effective in preparing all children starting from the preschool period and including children with mild special needs, for school. Arabzadeh, Abdolahi and Shamsedini-Lory (2016) conducted a study to examine the effect of the Philosophy for Children Program on the intelligence development of children in Tehran (as cited in Erdoğan, 2018). The participants of the study are preschool children in the age group of five and six. In the study, the Wechsler Intelligence Test was applied to the children and a total of 30 children with average intelligence were randomly selected and included in the study. There were 15 children in each of the experimental and control groups. Findings which was obtained at the end of the study, showed that the philosophy program for children significantly increased the verbal IQ levels of 5-6 year old preschool children. In other studies on this subject, It is stated that the university age is late to gain intellectual abilities and these skills should be acquired in childhood (Jackson, 2013; Karakaya, 2006; Valitalo, Juuso, & Sutinen 2015). In Mutlu's (2010) study, "The Investigation of the Thinking Levels of Children in Early Childhood (60-72 months) and Preschool Teachers' Attitudes towards Critical Thinking Education", it was stated that teachers have incomplete knowledge about the detailed purposes of "Critical Thinking education" and traditional views caused them to think negatively about it. This situation shows us the importance of using innovative approaches in education and that these approaches should be taught to teachers.

РЕЗУЛЬТАТИ І ВИСНОВКИ
Result and Conclusion

Philosophy education for children whose foundations were laid with the Socratic method, is used in many areas with starting from preschool. In philosophy education which

have been used actively in preschool education in recent years, programs are the basic elements. The program is indispensable in effective education process. Philosophy education for children provides an inquiry that goes from a single element to the general based on a text and to discuss the text conceptually. The selection of texts such as children's novels, short stories, poems, newspaper news, essays to be used in this education is important. The texts that will be used to philosophize with children should have some basic features. For instance, the texts should be relevant to the daily life of the children, should be appropriate for the ages of the children and should not contain abstractions that children cannot understand. In addition, philosophical concepts such as happiness and friendship, which are in children's lives and are easier to understand, should be hidden in the events in the text. The characters in the texts should be a model for children during questioning. These characters should be ordinary, everyday people. Furthermore, the process should be well planned (Akkocaoğlu Çayır, 2015; Özkan, 2020).

Philosophy has clear cognitive goals for children. Philosophy forces the mind to work. This is done through challenges, basic thinking, and structural interaction. The philosophy education program for children also has a social purpose that teaches democratic decision-making process to children. This program can ensure the development of the individual's consciousness by ensuring continuous participation. Teaching the critical thinking skills can be considered as the most general and obvious goal of this program. From Lipman's point of view, the most important goal of this program is to help children to learn how to think (Gaedi, 2015). In this study, it is tried to present an example of preparing a philosophy education program with considering the benefits of philosophy education in children.

As a result, if the preschool education program is prepared on the basis of different-innovative approaches and models, it will enrich and improve children's learning. In this study, it was tried to provide information about the stages of preparing a good philosophy program for preschool children. However, the study was limited to the analysis and development stages of the program. The application process is not included in the study. Therefore, future studies may include researches to test the program.

Литература References

- Akkocaoğlu Çayır, N. (2015). *Çocuklar İçin Felsefe Eğitimi Üzerine Nitel Bir Araştırma*, (Yayımlanmamış Doktora Tezi), Hacettepe Üniversitesi: Ankara.
- Boyacı, N. P.; Karadağ, F.; Gülenç, K. (2018). "Çocuklar İçin Felsefe / Çocuklarla Felsefe," *Kaygı*, 31/2018: 145-173.
- Demirtaş, V. Y., Karadağ, F., Gülenç, K. (2018). "Levels Of The Questions Formulated By Preschool Children During the Philosophical Inquiry Process and the Qualities of Their Answers: Philosophy With Children", *International Online Journal of Educational Sciences*, 10(2).
- Direk, N. (2016). *Küçük prens üzerine düşünmek (6. Baskı)*. İstanbul: Pan Yayınları.
- Erdoğan, P. (2018). *Çocuklarla Felsefe Yaklaşımının Düşünsel, Tarihi ve Sosyal Temelleri Üzerine Bir İnceleme*. Ankara Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü Eğitimin Kültürel Temelleri Anabilim Dalı Eğitim Felsefesi Programı Yüksek Lisans Tezi. Ankara.
- Gaedi, Y. (2015). The nature of philosophy for children and its role in teaching and learning, *Philosophy Study*, 5 (6), 292-296. DOI: 10.17265/2159-5313/2015.06.004
- Jackson, T. E. (2013). Home Grown. *Educational Perspectives*(44), s. 3-7.
- Karakaya, Z. (2006). Günümüz Çocuk Edebiyatından Seçilmiş Çocuk Felsefesi Örnekleri. *Türkoloji Dergisi*(2), 21-39.
- Lipman, M. (2003). *Thinking in Education*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.

McCall, C. C. (2013). *Transforming Thinking: Philosophical Inquiry in the Primary and Secondary Classroom*, Routledge. (Düşünmeyi Dönüştürmek: İlk ve Orta Sınıflarda Felsefi Sorgulama, çev. Kurtul Gülenç & Nihal Petek Boyacı, 2017).

Mutlu, E. (2010). *Erken Çocukluk Dönemindeki Çocukların (60-72 ay) Düşünme Düzeylerinin ve Okul Öncesi Öğretmenlerinin Düşünme Eğitimi Ile İlgili Tutumlarının İncelenmesi*. (yayımlanmamış yüksek lisans tezi). Onsekiz Mart Üniversitesi, Çanakkale.

Öğüt, F. (2019). *Felsefi düşünmenin önemi ve çocuklar için felsefe* (Doktora Tezi, Maltepe Üniversitesi, Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü, İstanbul, Türkiye). <http://tez.yok.gov.tr/UlusalTezMerkezi/>'nden elde edilmiştir. (Tez No. 595272).

Özkan, B. (2020). Çocuklar için felsefe neden önemlidir? *Ulusal Eğitim Akademisi Dergisi (UEAD)*, 4(1), 49-61.

Valitalo, R., Juuso, H., & Sutinen, A. (2015). *Philosophy For Children As An Educational Practice*. Springer, 79-92.

Wartenberg, T. E. (2014). *Big ideas for little kids: Teaching philosophy through children's literature*. Rowman & Littlefield.

